

Exploring Performance and User Experience in Haptic Teleoperation Systems: A Study on QoS/QoE Dynamics on Immersive Communications

Fernando Hernandez-Goberti*, Raul Lozano*, Konstantinos Kousias[†],
Özgü Alay[†], Carsten Griwodz[†], David Gomez-Barquero*

*iTEAM Research Institute, Universitat Politècnica de València, Valencia, Spain
{fahergob, raulote, dagobar}@iteam.upv.es

[†]Department of Informatics, Universitetet i Oslo, Oslo, Norway
{konstako, ozgua, griff}@ifi.uio.no

Abstract—Haptic teleoperation systems mark a critical breakthrough in remote manipulation technologies, delivering immersive user experiences through precise control and tactile feedback. This paper aims to explore the interplay between Quality of Service (QoS) network metrics, such as latency, jitter, and packet loss, and Quality of Experience (QoE) features, including immersion, control, and engagement. This investigation is conducted through a combination of objective measurements and subjective evaluations over a private Fifth Generation Standalone (5G SA) network. In addition, it aims to realize the extent to which transport-layer protocols operating over IP, such as TCP and UDP, as well as environmental factors like indoor and outdoor settings, influence system performance.

Results confirm the well-established trade-off between reliability and latency in transport protocols, with TCP offering higher reliability in controlled indoor environments, and UDP exhibiting better responsiveness in dynamic outdoor scenarios. While these findings align with existing knowledge, their empirical validation in the context of immersive haptic applications over a private 5G SA network reinforces their relevance. In addition, QoE metrics were found to be linked to QoS indicators, highlighting the importance of balancing speed, stability, and reliability. These findings provide valuable insights towards designing adaptive teleoperation systems capable of dynamically optimizing performance under diverse conditions.

Index Terms—Haptic teleoperation, 5G Immersive communications, Measurements

I. INTRODUCTION

Haptic teleoperation systems are transforming remote manipulation by enabling users to interact with distant environments through real-time force feedback and precise control [1]. These systems integrate robotic manipulators, haptic devices, and networked communication to enable immersive and intuitive operation, in verticals such as industrial automation [2], furnace maintenance [3], and neutralization of explosives [4]. However, their effectiveness is highly dependent on QoS parameters that have a direct influence on user-perceived QoE [5]. The increasing adoption of 5G/B5G networks has improved the feasibility of bilateral teleoperation by providing ultra-low latency, high reliability, and adaptive bandwidth [6], yet challenges remain in optimizing system performance

Fig. 1. Foundational communications structure for haptic teleoperation systems as defined by the recent IEEE Standard for Haptic Codecs for the Tactile Internet 1918.1 [7].

under different environmental conditions and communication protocols.

The fundamental structure of these systems is presented in Figure 1. This framework highlights three essential components (from left to right): Tactile Devices, which generate and receive force-feedback signals; Tactile Edge, responsible for processing and synchronizing data; and Network Infrastructure, which transmits control commands and sensory information. In this scenario, the choice of transport protocol is critical for maintaining stability and responsiveness for haptic teleoperation systems. The trade-off between reliability and latency in transport-layer protocols is well-known, with TCP offering greater reliability at the cost of higher latency, and UDP favoring lower latency with the risk of packet loss. However, empirical validation of this trade-off in the context of immersive haptic applications over SA networks is essential to guide protocol selection for QoS/QoE-aware deployments [8].

This paper systematically investigates the impact of communication protocols and environmental factors on a representative haptic teleoperation system. While the scope is

focused on a specific type of haptic system and controlled environmental setups, this allows for in-depth analysis and empirical validation that can serve as a foundation for broader investigations involving diverse feedback mechanisms and hardware configurations.

Using a private 5G SA network, we conduct objective QoS measurements and subjective QoE evaluations across both indoor and outdoor environments. While these settings do not capture the full diversity of real-world scenarios, such as urban areas with high interference, rural regions with limited coverage, or mobile use cases involving dynamic movement, they offer controlled conditions to isolate and analyze the effects of protocol selection on user experience. Unlike previous studies, we employ statistical modeling, including mixed-effects and factor analysis, to identify key performance trends and quantify correlations between network behavior and perceived usability.

II. RELATED WORK

Haptic teleoperation has been extensively studied in the context of remote manipulation, particularly regarding its dependence on network QoS metrics such as latency, jitter, and packet loss. Prior studies have demonstrated that maintaining low latency is critical for real-time applications, with thresholds below 50 ms being necessary for effective manipulation tasks [9]. Jitter has also been identified as a major factor affecting haptic feedback consistency, with variations above 10 ms significantly degrading the user experience [10]. While these works establish the fundamental relationship between network performance and system usability, they primarily focus on controlled environments and do not explore the interplay between different communication protocols under varying environmental conditions.

In terms of communication protocol optimization, existing studies highlight trade-offs between TCP/UDP in teleoperation scenarios. TCP ensures reliable packet delivery but introduces additional latency due to retransmissions, whereas UDP provides lower latency at the cost of increased packet loss [11]. Recent efforts have explored hybrid approaches that dynamically switch between these protocols based on network conditions, aiming to balance reliability and responsiveness [12]. However, these solutions rely on static adaptation mechanisms and lack a thorough statistical analysis of how protocol choices impact objective performance and subjective user perception in real-world settings.

The influence of environmental conditions on haptic teleoperation also remains an area of active research. Studies conducted in outdoor scenarios have shown that increased signal attenuation and interference can result in latency increases of up to 50% compared to indoor settings, particularly in non-line-of-sight (NLOS) conditions. Furthermore, mobility and network variability further exacerbate packet loss and jitter, negatively affecting user experience [13]. While prior works acknowledge these challenges, there is limited research that systematically quantifies their impact across different protocol configurations using rigorous statistical methods.

III. EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

The experimental study developed focuses on bilateral teleoperation, as depicted in Figure 2. The Local Control and Orchestration Node (LCON) is placed indoors in UPV's Immersive Laboratory, while the Remote Teleoperation and Haptic Node (RTHN) is dynamically placed in different areas of the UPV campus, including both indoor and outdoor scenarios. The system integrates advanced robotic manipulation, real-time tracking, and vibrotactile feedback, enabling remote object manipulation with increased precision and low latency. The architecture combines state-of-the-art communication protocols and Machine Learning (ML) techniques (i.e., CNN-based gesture recognition) to ensure synchronized operation between the remote user and the robotic system.

A. System Components

At the RTHN, a RealSense camera captures video at 720p and 30 fps. The captured data undergoes processing through a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)-based gesture recognition system that was trained with over 12,000 annotated samples using MediaPipe's pre-trained hand landmark model, fine-tuned on a custom dataset collected in our lab. This enables the extraction of 3D hand key points to implement camera-based hand tracking. The detected gestures are mapped into control signals for the robotic system via tracking control algorithms, ensuring precise and responsive interaction. Additionally, the node integrates bHaptics TactGloves, which utilize six linear resonant actuators for vibrotactile feedback. The haptic feedback system dynamically adjusts parameters such as duration, intensity, and actuator selection based on the physical state of the robotic gripper and tracking system. These adjustments are handled through a dedicated glove controller integrated with the bHaptics Player API.

The LCON features a UR5e robotic arm with six degrees of freedom, paired with an OnRobot RG2 Gripper for precise manipulation tasks. Communication with these devices is managed using Modbus RTU and RTDE protocols, ensuring low-latency and reliable operation. Advanced controllers govern robotic arm's joint movements and Cartesian trajectories, employing inverse kinematics to achieve goal-based positioning. For gripping tasks, hybrid control models combine dynamic movement primitives and impedance control to adaptively manage the gripper's width, initial force, and duration during manipulation. The orchestration of these components is facilitated by Robot Operating System (ROS), which acts as communication backbone, while an XML-RPC server ensures efficient handling of Remote Procedure Calls (RPCs) using Extensible Markup Language (XML) messages for gripper control. Moreover, specialized controllers are in place to define robot trajectories and map gripper movements, ensuring precise coordination between the robot and the user.

B. Network Configuration

The experimental setup utilizes two outdoor nodes and two indoor nodes to provide coverage in the Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV) Campus, as shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 2. Experimental setup for the haptic teleoperation system integrating a Local Control and Orchestration Node (LCON) for robot management, and a Remote Teleoperation & Haptic Node (RTHN) for user interaction. Both nodes are connected via a private 5G SA network, with the LCON operating on n78 (indoor) and the RTHN operating either on n78 (indoor) or n40 (outdoor) band. The 5G network ensures real-time video, audio, tracking, and haptic data exchange using RTSP (for video/audio) and TCP/UDP (for control frames).

Fig. 3. General overview of the distribution of outdoor nodes and indoor femtocells on the UPV Campus where measurements were performed.

These nodes operate in Standalone (SA) mode, leveraging both 5G Radio and Core infrastructure. The radio equipments are manufactured by Nokia, whereas the Core (common for all the nodes) relies on the open-source solution Open5GS. The two outdoor nodes operate in the n40 band (2380 MHz frequency, 20 MHz bandwidth), strategically positioned to provide network coverage across part of the Campus. On the other hand, the two indoor nodes operate in the n78 band (3550 MHz frequency, 100 MHz bandwidth), providing focused coverage within the Immersive Lab through two strategically placed pico-antennas.

In our experiments, the sequential communication through the network begins with the Hand Tracking system (part of the RTHN) generating spatial and temporal data, which is transmitted via the 5G network to the Robot Arm (LCON). Here, the data input triggers robotic actuation, and the Gripper Control responds by sending feedback, such as grip force

Fig. 4. Sequential communication configuration for teleoperation system illustrates interaction flow between components in haptic teleoperation loop.

and object dynamics, to the Haptic Gloves (back to RTHN). This synchronized communication loop, depicted in Figure 4, ensures that every action is timestamped to maintain precise coordination between user input and robotic response.

C. Experiment Design and User Study

We evaluated haptic teleoperation performance across four experimental scenarios, using two transport-layer protocols (TCP, UDP) and two environments (indoor, outdoor). The indoor environment provided stable network conditions, while the outdoor environment introduced variability such as signal attenuation and interference.

Our study included 20 participants, aged 20 to 40 years, with an average age of 30 and a balanced gender distribution. 70% of the participants had prior experience with haptic or

virtual systems, ensuring familiarity with the experimental interface. Each participant performed the same set of tasks across all four scenarios, starting with a 5-minute acclimatization phase to familiarize themselves with the system. Each session lasted approximately 15 minutes (including 1-minute pauses), followed by a survey completion to collect subjective feedback. Each participant performed object manipulation tasks using a UR5e robotic arm with an OnRobot RG2 gripper, following predefined trajectory-based tasks to assess precision, responsiveness, and user experience.

Objective metrics, such as latency, jitter, and packet loss, were recorded using network analysis tools (i.e., *ping* and *iperf*). Latency was measured from gesture detection in the Hand Tracking module (RTHN) to the reception of the command in the Robot Arm (LCON). Similarly, jitter and packet loss were quantified between the same modules. All three metrics were logged throughout the 100 experimental sessions (25 per scenario).

Subjective metrics were captured via post-task surveys. Participants rated their perceptions of immersion (“How immersed did you feel in the teleoperation task?”), control (“How precise and responsive was the control of the robotic arm?”), and engagement (“How involved and engaged did you feel while performing the task?”) on a 5-point Likert scale.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

The experimental study results provide in-depth insights on the interplay between network performance, environmental conditions, and user experience in haptic teleoperation systems. Further analyses on QoS metrics, their influence on QoE, and the interdependencies are revealed through statistical analysis.

A. Network Performance: Protocols & Environmental Effects

The evaluation of latency, jitter, and packet loss across TCP and UDP and indoor and outdoor environments revealed significant performance differences. Figure 5(a) illustrates that UDP consistently achieved lower latency in both environments, averaging 103.65 ms indoors and 110.12 ms outdoors, compared to TCP’s 107.47 ms indoors and 120.58 ms outdoors.

For further in-depth domain specification, SINR evolution was analyzed in parallel across different campus areas to assess signal consistency and its impact on packet-level performance, as shown in Figure 5(b). SINR measurements indicate a higher variability in outdoor scenarios, possibly due to higher interference and propagation complexity.

Reliability analysis revealed that UDP’s lower latency came at the cost of increased packet loss, particularly in outdoor scenarios where network variability was higher. Packet loss remained negligible indoors but reached 0.8% for UDP outdoors, while TCP’s loss is zero due to its retransmission mechanism, highlighting its robustness against environmental interference. These findings reinforce the trade-off between speed and reliability, with TCP favoring stability while UDP prioritizing responsiveness.

Fig. 5. (a) Mixed-effects modelings for latency distribution that evaluates the impact of protocol and configuration on network performance. (b) Temporal evolution of SINR values on different indoor and outdoor locations covered by UPV’s 5G SA private network.

To further analyze network variability, a jitter analysis was performed. Jitter, calculated as the average of the absolute differences between consecutive latency samples, confirmed that TCP maintained more stable packet timing indoors (2.7 ms) due to its flow control and error recovery mechanisms, while UDP’s jitter reached up to 8 ms. In outdoor conditions, TCP jitter increased to 5 ms, while UDP exhibited even greater variability (10.5 ms). These results confirm the well-known premise that UDP is preferable in controlled environments, while TCP performs better in unpredictable network conditions.

B. Protocol Impact on Task Completion Efficiency

Task completion efficiency, defined as the time required to manipulate objects along a predefined trajectory, serves as a practical metric to evaluate the impact of network protocols on teleoperation performance. This analysis, shown in Figure 6, assumes that a shorter completion time indicates better task efficiency, as users can execute actions with fewer interruptions or corrections. Tasks were standardized across participants to ensure comparability, and each participant performed same set of tasks under both UDP/TCP protocols, within similar environmental conditions.

In indoor scenarios, participants achieved high task efficiency, completing tasks in an average of 45 seconds under UDP and 48 seconds under TCP. These results indicate UDP’s reduced latency and more immediate feedback facilitate smoother task execution, allowing participants to make

Fig. 6. Task completion efficiency under different protocols and environments. The bars represent the average task completion times in seconds, with error bars indicating the standard deviation of performance.

precise adjustments in real time. In contrast, TCP’s retransmissions, while ensuring reliable data delivery, introduced slight delays in feedback, increasing task duration marginally.

Outdoor scenarios amplified these differences, with UDP configurations averaging 63 seconds per task and TCP reaching 75 seconds. The increased environmental variability in outdoor settings (e.g., signal interference and attenuation) led to higher latency and jitter for both protocols. For UDP, these conditions occasionally resulted in mismatched feedback, requiring additional user corrections. Meanwhile, TCP’s retransmission mechanism, while mitigating errors, further delayed feedback, disrupting the natural flow of manipulation and compounding task completion times.

The observed differences in task completion times reflect the varying QoS characteristics of UDP and TCP and their influence on user performance. While UDP consistently outperforms TCP in controlled indoor environments, its sensitivity to environmental changes outdoors can diminish its advantage. These findings suggest that while UDP’s low-latency design is well-suited for teleoperation tasks requiring responsiveness, a hybrid protocol approach that balances UDP’s speed with TCP’s reliability could enhance task efficiency and user experience in more challenging environments.

C. Subjective QoE Evaluation

User feedback on immersion, control, and engagement revealed significant differences between protocols and environments. Figure 7 shows that UDP in indoor settings achieved the highest Immersion and Engagement scores, with a median of 4 on a 5-point scale, reflecting the benefits of low-latency transmission. In contrast, outdoor scenarios exhibited a noticeable decline in QoE metrics, particularly under higher jitter and packet loss conditions. TCP performed better in Control ratings, suggesting that its reliability enhances task precision, even at the cost of higher latency.

A statistical analysis confirmed these differences. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) tests indicated that protocol and envi-

Fig. 7. Boxplots of subjective QoE scores for immersion, control, and engagement across the four configurations. Statistical significance tests confirm that differences between configurations are significant ($p < 0.05$).

ronment significantly impact all QoE dimensions ($p < 0.05$). Table I summarizes statistical scores across configurations, showing UDP indoors leads in Immersion and Engagement, while TCP indoors achieves best Control ratings. Outdoor configurations saw a drop in all metrics, with TCP slightly outperforming UDP in maintaining Control under fluctuating network conditions.

TABLE I
STATISTICS OF QoE METRICS BY CONFIGURATION

	Configuration	Median	Mean	Str. Dev.	IQ Range
Immersion	UDP – IN	4	4.2	0.6	4–5
	TCP – IN	4	3.9	0.7	3–4
	UDP – OUT	3	3.4	0.8	2–4
	TCP – OUT	3	3.2	0.7	2–3
Control	UDP – IN	4	4.1	0.7	3–4
	TCP – IN	4	4.3	0.6	4–5
	UDP – OUT	3	2.9	0.8	2–3
	TCP – OUT	3	3.0	0.7	2–3
Engagement	UDP – IN	4	4.4	0.5	4–5
	TCP – IN	4	4.2	0.6	3–4
	UDP – OUT	3	3.0	0.7	2–4
	TCP – OUT	3	3.3	0.6	2–3

Pairwise comparisons in Table II further validate these findings, showing that UDP and TCP perform similarly in controlled indoor conditions, but UDP degrades faster outdoors due to its susceptibility to packet loss and jitter. A Tukey post-hoc test confirmed that the difference between indoor and outdoor setups was statistically significant ($p < 0.01$), reinforcing the impact of environmental factors on user experience. These results suggest that while low-latency protocols enhance immersion, maintaining stability is equally crucial for precise teleoperation tasks.

D. Correlation Analysis between QoS and QoE

The analysis of QoS parameters and QoE metrics reveals strong correlations between latency, jitter, and packet

TABLE II
PAIRWISE P-VALUES FOR QOE METRIC COMPARISONS

Comparison	Immersion	Control	Engagement
UDP-IN vs. TCP-IN	0.06	0.03	0.07
UDP-IN vs. UDP-OUT	0.001	0.0001	0.0002
TCP-IN vs. TCP-OUT	0.003	0.002	0.005
UDP-OUT vs. TCP-OUT	0.4	0.2	0.3

loss with user experience. Figure 8 shows that latency has the strongest negative correlation (-0.76) with immersion, meaning that higher delays disrupt the real-time perception of teleoperation tasks. This aligns with previous findings that low-latency responses are essential for maintaining user engagement in haptic systems. A critical threshold of 110 ms was identified, beyond which immersion scores declined significantly, reinforcing the importance of strict latency control in teleoperation.

Jitter also has a significant negative impact on control (correlation of -0.62), as shown in Figure 9. Higher jitter values introduce inconsistencies in haptic feedback, leading to a noticeable reduction in task precision and responsiveness. When jitter exceeded 30 ms, users reported increased difficulty in maintaining smooth interactions, highlighting the need for stable packet delivery in teleoperation systems. While packet loss had a weaker correlation with QoE metrics, it still negatively affected all dimensions, particularly in outdoor scenarios, where environmental interference was more pronounced.

A multivariate regression model was used to quantify the combined effects of these QoS parameters, achieving an R^2 value of 0.81, indicating strong predictive power. The model confirmed latency and jitter explain 65% of the variance in QoE scores, with latency being the dominant factor for immersion and jitter for control. Packet loss, though less influential, still accounted for an additional 16% of variance, suggesting minimizing packet drops is essential for preserving overall user experience. These insights emphasize a complex interplay between network performance and user perception, reinforcing need for QoS-aware teleoperation frameworks. Threshold analysis suggests that maintaining latency below 50 ms, jitter below 30 ms, and packet loss under 1% provides the best QoE outcomes.

V. DISCUSSION

The results demonstrate the trade-offs between communication protocols, environmental conditions, and user experience in haptic teleoperation. UDP's lower latency makes it well-suited for real-time control in stable indoor settings, where minimal packet loss ensures smooth feedback. However, in outdoor environments with higher signal variability, TCP provides better reliability, mitigating packet loss and jitter spikes. This suggests that protocol selection should be dynamically adapted to environmental conditions, rather than relying on a fixed approach.

Fig. 8. Strength of the relationships between QoS metrics (Latency, Jitter, and Packet Loss) and QoE dimensions (Immersion, Control, and Satisfaction).

Fig. 9. Correlation Heatmap of QoS Metrics and QoE Outcomes, illustrating the relationships between QoS metrics and QoE dimensions. Darker shades indicate stronger correlations, with red representing positive correlations and blue indicating negative correlations.

Environmental factors play a crucial role in teleoperation performance, with outdoor conditions significantly increasing latency and jitter. Even with 5G SA, signal fluctuations and interference introduce performance degradation that directly affects user experience. Network slicing and adaptive resource allocation could help mitigate these effects, ensuring low-latency and stable connections even in challenging deployment scenarios. Additionally, leveraging edge computing to preprocess haptic feedback could reduce the impact of network-induced delays.

The findings also highlight that task requirements influence

the ideal communication strategy. Applications demanding high-speed interaction and immersion, such as remote surgery or industrial telemanipulation, benefit from low-latency protocols like UDP. Conversely, tasks prioritizing precision and data integrity, such as hazardous environment exploration, may tolerate slightly higher delays in exchange for more consistent control. Future research should explore task-aware protocol switching mechanisms, allowing teleoperation systems to adapt dynamically based on operational needs.

While this study provides valuable insights, further investigation is needed to generalize these findings across different teleoperation setups, hardware configurations, and network conditions. Exploring multi-path communication strategies, where multiple transport protocols operate concurrently, could improve robustness in variable environments. Additionally, long-term user studies assessing learning curves and adaptation over time would provide a more comprehensive understanding of QoE evolution in teleoperation scenarios.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This work evaluated the interplay between communication protocols, environmental conditions, and user experience in a haptic teleoperation system featuring video-based tracking and vibrotactile feedback. The experiments provided actionable insights into QoS/QoE dynamics, highlighting trade-offs between speed and reliability in varying operational contexts. UDP proved superior in scenarios prioritizing low latency, while TCP excelled when requiring robust data integrity.

Overall, the findings underscore the trade-offs between responsiveness and reliability in haptic teleoperation. While UDP provides a more immersive experience, its performance deteriorates in variable network conditions, making hybrid approaches or adaptive transport strategies a promising direction for improvement. Future work should explore real-time network adaptation techniques that optimize protocol selection based on task complexity and user requirements to maintain high QoE across diverse scenarios.

Recognizing the growing relevance of modern transport technologies, future research should also incorporate comparative analyses with protocols such as QUIC [14], a standardized IETF protocol increasingly adopted across the Internet, designed to address the limitations of traditional TCP and UDP, combining low-latency performance with improved reliability and connection management. Evaluating QUIC in the context of haptic teleoperation could yield valuable insights into its suitability for immersive, real-time applications. Future work should also explore emerging frameworks such as IEEE Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN), which offers end-to-end latency and reliability guarantees that may further enhance the performance of haptic communication systems, especially in industrial or safety-critical settings.

Beyond protocol-level enhancements, machine learning techniques can be employed to predict QoS variations and proactively adjust transport configurations, ensuring stable teleoperation quality even under dynamic conditions. Context-aware decision-making integrated into the control framework

could enable higher levels of responsiveness and reliability, improving overall system usability.

Lastly, expanding the participant pool to include a broader range of demographics, skill levels, and physical abilities would offer a more comprehensive understanding of system usability and accessibility. This would support the development of more inclusive and adaptable haptic teleoperation solutions for real-world applications.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was partially supported by the Spanish Ministry of Economic Affairs and Digital Transformation and the European Union-NextGenerationEU through the UNICO 5G I+D ADVANCING-5G-IMMERSIVE (TSI-063000-2021-109, TSI-063000-2021-110, TSI-063000-2021-111) project, and by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme (HORIZON-MSCA-2022-DN-01) through the TOAST project under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 101073465, and by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme (HORIZON-JU-SNS-2022) through the IMAGINE-B5G project under the grant agreement No. 101096452.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. A. Hernández Goberti, "Immersive teleoperation of a robotic arm with grip recognition and haptic feedback," *Academic Repository of Universitat Politècnica de València*, 2024.
- [2] W. Fan, X. Guo, E. Feng *et al.*, "Digital twin-driven mixed reality framework for immersive teleoperation with haptic rendering," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, 2023.
- [3] J. Park, I. S. Choi, S.-W. Choi *et al.*, "Adaptive haptic control interface for safeguarding robotic teleoperation in hazardous steelmaking environments," in *2024 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 15 721–15 727.
- [4] K. Feng, Q. Xu *et al.*, "Design and development of a teleoperated telepresence robot system with high-fidelity haptic feedback assistance," *IEEE Transactions on Automation Science and Engineering*, 2024.
- [5] A. Anwar, T. Shi, and O. Schneider, "Factors of haptic experience across multiple haptic modalities," in *Proceedings of the 2023 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 2023, pp. 1–12.
- [6] M. Emami, A. Bayat, R. Tafazolli *et al.*, "A survey on haptics: Communication, sensing and feedback," *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 2024.
- [7] IEEE Standards Association: IEEE Standard for Haptic Codecs for the Tactile Internet (IEEE 1918.1.1-2024).
- [8] D. Liu, J. Kim, and Y. Ham, "Multi-user immersive environment for excavator teleoperation in construction," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 156, p. 105143, 2023.
- [9] D. G. Black, D. Andjelic, and S. E. Salcudean, "Evaluation of communication and human response latency for (human) teleoperation," *IEEE Transactions on Medical Robotics and Bionics*, 2024.
- [10] M. Awais, F. Ullah Khan, M. Zafar *et al.*, "Towards enabling haptic communications over 6g: Issues and challenges," *Electronics*, vol. 12, no. 13, p. 2955, 2023.
- [11] E. Sariyildiz, F. Hanss, H. Zhou *et al.*, "Experimental evaluation of a hybrid sensory feedback system for haptic and kinaesthetic perception in hand prostheses," *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 20, p. 8492, 2023.
- [12] I. Abdullah and W. Monnet, "An emulation framework for haptic data transmission using real-time transport protocol," *International Journal of Online & Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 19, no. 7, 2023.
- [13] X. Limani, N. Slamnik-Kriještorac, T. van de Ven *et al.*, "Optimizing 5g-based teleoperation: Synergy of vulnerable road user awareness and advanced traffic management systems," in *EuCNC/6G Summit*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 1067–1072.
- [14] Y. Luo, C. Liu, Y. J. Lee *et al.*, "Adaptive tactile interaction transfer via digitally embroidered smart gloves," *Nature communications*, vol. 15, no. 1, p. 868, 2024.